

Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory Protocol

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Abstract:

This work is done for the new entrepreneurship company building strategies in applied chemistry as a part of the Laboratory Project in Jordan university of science and technology. The protocol focusing on the building strategies of the company in Az-zunayyah town in Jordan, it depend on the characterization of the study as the geochemistry, environment chemistry, green chemistry, analytical chemistry, surveys, and case studies. This protocol contain six procedures for each part of the study methodology. As it's the study determined for the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution Philosophy thesis.

Introduction:

The world go towards the new idea in Corona virus pandemic in the bachelor student teaching for the laboratory in applied chemistry in some countries. This idea is the home-based laboratory that was found in the ancient scientists and philosophy, and this idea will be activated in Jordan as the first time applied in Jordan as set in Az-zunayyah

town in Almafraq city. However, the idea application based on the seventh discussion paper of the king of Jordan Abdullah II bin AL Hussain. And the institution building to make my ideas, hopeness, love, patience, and curiosity act really and imaginary. This protocol is applied for the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory infrastructure building as the research home-based laboratory include the literature review of the madness laboratory modern ideas and applications.

Materials and methods:

Monkey survey, facebook, 200g soil, brass plate in the GOR by the thickness 1cm, width is 20 cm and length is 30cm, ground penetration radar, 1m sand, thermometer, gas chromatography, ice, hot plate, 7000ml distilled water, Li, Na, Fe, Co, Cu, As, Cl, Al, F lumps, atomic absorption spectroscopy, gelatin, veniger, saucepan, anemometer, refrigerator, drill tools for well building, camera, gloves, google earth, recycling container, interview papers, traffic money costs.

Procedure:

In this section the procedures data will be determined for the study so go to it; firstly the survey procedure, where in seven questions available to be answered by no or yes in the determined especial questionnaire for specified in Arabian language with good background of the new idea to be taken, and these questions are:

Note: "Th home-based laboratory is a new idea come from Corona virus pandemic to solve the problem that there is no available sharing working between student, and I make as the entrepreneurship idea based on new world and on the seventh discussion paper of King Abdullah II bin AL Hussain, and based on the using of home chemicals and instruments to make Arabian culture with Arabian character of undefined professor."

- Are the mission of you agree with building home-based laboratory?
- Are your vision agree with the building of new home-based laboratory?
- Does it caused any defects in the town function, or on you?
- Does it help to feed your culture and growth for it?
- Are it caused toxic and hazardous feelings on your policies?
- Are you give me the chance to explore the universe?
- Are you want to become a one of the team?

Then the environmental chemistry will be set and taken as the procedure below:

1. The soil type:

- Soil colloids:

Get the beaker mass then add 25 g of soil, add to 200 ml distilled water, then avoiding the foaming add 10-20H₂O₂, then leave it at room temperature for 2 days. After that, heat to 80°C in the fume hood to remove the H₂O₂. Then dry in oven for 24 hours at 105°C, then using graduated cylinder and blank sample (1:99 soil to distilled water) then mix the soil (suspension) and left it for 10 second then insert the hydrometer, after that, record reading at each 20seconds five times then make the average.

- Soil cation and anion exchange:

Divided the earth into specific areas by 1m² then take from each one from the center a sample by 5 g, mix the samples then take 1 g from the mixture. Then will be add to it drops of water in porcelain dish and drops of 10% HCl add, if bubbles appear the soil is carbonate. Then take another 2 g sample of soil in test tube with 10ml HCl with 0.2 M, then

after that shaken then filtrate then add 2% BaCl₂ and shaken then the white precipitates of BaSO₄ appear so it gypsum. For another sample getting from soil use 1g soil and 5 g distilled water then shaken for 3 minutes then filtrate, add 10% H₂SO₄ drops then few drops of 5% AgNO₃ and shaken, if appear white precipitate of AgCl then it salty

- Soil acidity:

The land must be designed to be in 1 m² imaginary, then take from each area a one gram of soil from the center to collect 10 g soil, then mix it and take a sample of 1 g. then make the solution from it by distilled water and mix the solution carefully by the volume is 50ml. Put the pH device column then measure the results, by using the curve of the calibration scale measure the acidity of the soil.

- Soil salinity:

Drying soil at 105°C for 24 hours, then take 200g of it then put it in container with lid and saturated it by deionized water to become saturated, then let the equilibrium occur for 4 hours, then if there is water add soil and if there is soil dried add water in saturation state. After that, take it for other 4 hours then make filtration by Büchner funnel and extract soil by centrifuge. After that, put the conductivity electric cell column in it and read the EC.

2. The water available:

- If there is groundwater. By using ground-penetrating radar, connect it with USB with laptop, using the object of brass plate in the GOR by the thickness 1cm, width is 20 cm and length is 30cm. And make the trench

by length is 100cm, and width is 50cm and by the sand layer put by the depth is 1cm. Then make the exploration and determine the graph.

- If there is no groundwater. Make the ground well and filled it by the water sources such as the winter, make the tap also as the source directly connected to the ground well.

3. The heat range:

- By using thermometer clean it by distilled water then dry it, then make it free in the air without connections.
- Take the temperature value at each hour from 6 o'clock to the second day at 6 o'clock then set it in the table.
- Take different reading in the sides of the area surrounding the institution place, and in the entrance of the surrounding. Then scaling it carefully.

4. The air system and components ratio:

- The sample will be collecting from different areas in Az-zunayyah and from the institution place for different days at different temperatures by using sampling pump.
- Using the gas chromatography: the sample injected in the port by the hypodermic syringe, then heated until gas phase transfer to the column by the carrier gas (Helium), once the chromatogram appear determined the types of the gases and its amount with ratio.

5. Trace elements in the water:

- Take sample of the water from its sources by the lid of the bottle in different times (morning, afternoon...) and different days (cold, hot), one from the top of the ground wells, then from the depth distance, then

saved in the refrigerator until it transfer to the lab. The total sample is 500 ml.

- Take 50 ml filtered water then make it cold at -5°C , then measure the pH and calculate the curve with the heat of it, then determine the first point, the point in cold medium, and the point in the hot stage as the highest level of temperature in the town.
- Take 50 ml of water then add to it the tablespoon of vinegar, then boil it in the saucepan, make solution of unsaturated sugar/water then add it to the water, add two gelatin sheets to water until it dissolved, cooling agar for few hours. Take 50 sample of water, and set the candle around the system to avoid the air bacteria, then zigzag put some points of water on the agar and put the lid, set it for 5 days in a warm condition, then each points appear is a bacteria position.
- Take 5 ml of water. Take the lumps of the ions from the atoms are (Li, Na, Fe, Co, Cu, As, Cl, Al, F) then put the sample of the water and put it on the nebulizer and set the graph to detecting the salts ions.

1. Geographical analysis of the town and the institution:

- By using google earth and google maps, determine the map of Az-zunayyah and the position of the institution building, determine the mountains, the valleys, the plains, and buttes.
- By using google earth and anemometer determine the map of winds for the season with its name and determine these requirements on Az-zunayyah map and the institution position. These are:
 - The wind flow speed, the wind flow direction. And the wind flow strength.

Using the anemometer, place 100 m from the entrances of the institution place and measure the speed of winds, then set in the center of the place area and measure it by connected the anemometer to the laptop by USB and set the ter then Where wends direction is the rotation numbers, strength is the velocity of the rotation number, the direction is the angular position of the device.

- The winds flow density.

That is from the mole fractions % in the gas chromatography for the air, then convert it to mass and divided it by the volume, then multiplied it by the speed of winds cubic and divided by 2.

Then green chemistry will be set and take as the procedure below:

1. The rubbish ratio:

Calculate and take photos for the rubbish positions and determine the distributions with the ratio of the rubbish mass per area.

2. The rubbish quality: (inorganic, organic)

Take gloves and separate the rubbish surrounding the institution and the town then determine each of the organic materials in specific container and other for inorganic materials. Then physical process of crashing and separating of the sample set. Then take samples of the mixture after several mixing, then take the specral analysis.. The rubbish decomposition ratio:

The rubbish go to non-chemically process will be recycling and saved in another container. Must flow in the rules of the Trusted and high product sales exposure.

3. The rubbish goes to the recycling or no.

That can be recycling formulate the protocols of the recycling and new project to manufacturing it with the SWOT analysis for that. That can not goes to recycling write it with its ratio and distribution to be registered in the institution and send copy for the environment policemen, the head of the town, the municipality, as publish it publically.

Then the ethnography, where it will be used as the procedure below:

1. The mission ethnography analysis.

"The mission of Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory is the talents of the challenges in the curiosity of the applied chemistry functionalizes to the metaphysical nature of the new age of the world to judge the universe. And the imaginations to applied the reality of the nature and the hyper knowledge concentrated in the applied chemistry."

2. The vision ethnography analysis.

" First rule is the saturation of the imaginary applied chemistry by the Arabian cultural musical authenticity of the Arabian literature. Second rule is the discovering of the mysterious magical alchemy culture by applied physical chemistry and thermodynamics chemistry conceptual analysis. Third rule is the advisory in adventure of the metaphysics of applied chemistry sciences and subjects. Fourth rule is the applied the rules of Jordan vision in the seventh discussion paper."

The case study will be taken also include the agreements and the grants required, where its procedure is: include the laboratory building engineering also.

- Agreements.

A cover letter sends to the police office in Bala'ma, and the Almafraaq judgement include the mission of the institution and vision summary, and the safety rules of the institution with the policies of the institution.

- Grants.

E-mail sending with the cover letter and the proposal of the institution to the grants bodies in Jordan and global.

- Engineering building.

Simple mathematics, simple physics, and applied chemistry will be taken to design a new building for the applied chemistry and thermodynamics chemistry home-based laboratory focusing on the studies.

Data analysis methods

In this section I will investigated the data analysis methods used in the procedure application for the protocol of Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory institution philosophy that will be applied here in the chapter of the research studies results and discussions, and in this section I will get the good analysis of the calculations and steps of analysis spectral data as I will get the understanding of the procedure that will be used with the profile of the institutions in applied chemistry as the home-based laboratory building in Jordan, Az-zunayyah.

1. The survey of the public people in Az-zunayyah data analysis.

In this part data of the survey will be collected and make the diagram of the results in answers of yes and no, then the data will take its average and main values, set as the accuracy getting and the precision, then prepared the agreements of the people and disagreements and get each question in the survey a specific value by using the average value to evaluate the strength of the answers, then collect the strengths of them and take

the main and average values to compare it with the simple answers values and get the final agreements from the public. That will be designed in the institution profile and registered electronically by digital object identifier for the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory library as the reference profile.

2. The ethnography of the mission and the vision.

That will be separate each target and sentences from the vision and the mission, then get its values from the ethnography analysis of the values of its, then take the average and the main values, then multiplied each part with the values to get the strength of them, and then take the average and main for them and determined the accuracy with the precision of the world idea, then it will be saved as the institution profile and registered by the digital object identifier electronically.

3. Green chemistry.

Collect the rubbish quality with its ratio and determine for each one if it will be recycling, then measure the tendency to behave as the chemical recycling. Put the data in scale and determine the main and average values for the quantity for its variables of the ratio and tendency, then determine the strength of them by multiplied each value with the average and take the main values. After that, determined high quality materials, the high product and trusted materials, then the determination of the costs and the ratio acting, then the set of economics SWOT.

4. Environment chemistry.

- For the soil:
 - Soil salinity:

Take the values of the E_c of the samples for five times, record it in the table, then make the average value and the main value with the accuracy setting.

- Soil colloids:

Record the values for the hydrometer for five times after each 20 seconds, then take the average of the values and mentioned it with the accuracy of the study.

- Soil cations and anions exchange:

In the first step if bubbles appear the soil is carbonate. In the second step if the white precipitates of BaSO_4 appear so it gypsum. In the third step if appear white precipitate of AgCl then it salty.

- Soil acidity:

Drawing the pH diagram then take the pH value for the water in the endpoints, then determine the pH total value. Take the average and mean values, then determine the pKa value and the acidity of the water.

- For the air:

- The spectra reading for the chemicals in the air by the peaks determination, where each peak corresponding to specific atom, then search about it in the encyclopedia or in the references available data tables of the atoms in Gas Chromatography to determine each atom.
- The spectra reading for the amounts of each chemical by the length of each peaks, where it corresponds to specific concentration available in the dependent axis of the chromatogram.

- For the water:

- Water availability:

Read the spectra of ground-penetrating radar and determine if there is water, determine each of the water depth, sub-bottom sediment thickness, surface water/ground water

connection. And take the results. And if there is no ground well use the industrial ground make building with the source of the water as the tap on it, but must taken the water studies.

- Chemical compositions:

Firstly if the appear in the agar a porous points so there is bacteria ratios in the water. And the spectra of the water from the atomic absorption spectroscopy show the types of the elements of the salts in ion phase as the peaks, where each peak represent a one metal ion and the number of beaks represent the amount of it.

- Water acidity:

Drawing the pH diagram then take the pH value for the water in the endpoints, then determine the pH total value for it at specific required temperature for (-5°C, 0°C, 27°C, and 40°C). Take the average and mean values, then determine the pKa value and the acidity of the water.

- For the heat:

- Temperature range, main and average values, of the day and night.
- Temperature mapping of the surrounding.

Take the photo of the surrounding map, then determined the points of the measurements locations, then set the average temperature in each position and the location.

5. The case study.

- The agreements:

- Analyze are the basic requirements for the laboratory techniques and the methodologies of its working.
- Analyze possibility of the laboratory building in the town.

- Agreements level and protections:
 - Analyze policies detecting results:
 - Analyze agreements requirements (Documents, money, physical objects)
- The grants:

The grants determined by business proposal set by Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory and determine the mechanism of the managements system and design. And the library printed it, the proposal sent to the financial bodies in Jordan and Arabian countries as the European Union for different bodies in them. Determined the factors and the variables that are the business factors by the Canvas model analysis. Where the customer segments determined for the business, then connected by the values propositions that release to use it to identified the channels to design the customer relationships. After that, the Canvas model analysis determined the key partners to make the key resources by the key activities, and set the resume revenue and finally by the detection of the Canvas model analysis value by the costs.

- The engineering of the chemistry home-based laboratory.
 - Area of the home:

The area of the home is 49 m² and divided to four parts of it. Home is designed as a studio home, divided into four rooms one is the kitchen, the bedroom, and the living room with bathroom . With the walls surrounding the home place area and set on its top the sieve iron helical sheets and its length by the same as the home rooms lengths is 3.5 m². And Jermicula design for the walls surrounding the home, and the surface of the home to protected it, with iron doors avoid any penetration's and all the home protected by several cameras in different ways.

- Area of the lab:

According to the industry ministry of Jordan for personal home industry the maximum area for the home business is 25 m² . It take to be faraway from the lab area, take small areas of windows 20cm×1m, take iron sieve sheet for the windows and doors.

- Chemical protection methods:

The home components contain gases path, flame protection, flame protection walls painting. Moisture, temperature, pressure, winds, and other outer conditions of the home protected by the gypsum layer for heat and pressure, from winds by small windows and iron sieve sheet for the doors also by small porous, and moisture by bricks, air vents, roof ventilation tiles, ventilated soffits and window ven. Using also the water source for fire protection by water sprinkler in the top, and fire extinguisher and bathroom, with eyes washer.

6. Ethnography mission and vision:

- Thematic analysis

Become familiar with the data, generate initial codes, Search for themes, Review themes, Define themes, Write-up.

- Narrative analysis

Code narrative blocks. Group and read by live-event. Create a nested story structure. Delve into the story structure. Compare across story structure. Tell the core narrative.

- Discourse analysis

conduct detailed observations, take field notes, analyze interactions, interview key informants, conduct documentary analyses.

- Grounded theory

Firstly, the step must compare information of the vision and the mission with other from the starting of the introduction. Secondly, compare information that gathering with emerging categories. Thirdly, demonstrate relationships between concepts and categories

- Content analysis.

be immersed in the contexts, environment, situations, and lifeworld of the subjects. And the steps are ranged by coma from the first as, Decide the level of analysis, Decide how many concepts to code, Decide whether to code for existence or frequency of a concept, Decide on how you will distinguish among concepts, Develop rules for coding your texts, Decide what to do with irrelevant information, code the text, then analyze the results

Appendix one: 3D google earth map of Az-zunayyah.

98%

مسجد الصحابي
سلمان الفارسي

مسجد العليمات

الزيتية

مدرسة الزيتية
الثانوية للبنات

Alalimat Chemistry Laboratory

400 م

Appendix two: Az-zunayyah map.

Conclusion:

This study take place in Az-zunayyah town about the new idea formation depend on the mission and vision in global community and applications and starting with different scientific research books and literature in Arabian culture and artificial intelligence. The protocol describe the mechanisms of the experiments to set it in different stages and different research methodologies types.